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**HISTORY OF UNPRIVILEGED PALESTINE: A
RESEARCH REVIEW IN THE CONTEXT OF
RECENT HAMAS-ISRAEL WAR**

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HISTORY OF UNPRIVILEGED PALESTINIANS: A RESEARCH REVIEW IN THE CONTEXT OF RECENT HAMAD-ISRAEL WAR

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ABSTRACT

Today's Muslims are engulfed and conquered globally as a result of the malicious intent of their conquerors. They are now referred to as the world's downtrodden people. Given that Palestine is a contentious topic involving Muslims, Christians, and Jews, these colonialists specifically target the Muslims living in Palestine. For all of them, it is a holy and precious location. In addition to considering this land to be their inheritance, Jews have long attempted to establish themselves thereby oppressing Palestinian Muslims, according to their political and social self-interests. The Muslims of Palestine are continuously subjected to oppression by the unlawful Israeli (Jewish) state in Jerusalem. These Palestinian Muslims are also referred to be the world's persecuted people because of their oppression. The issue of persecution in Palestine is becoming increasingly widespread these days. Muslims are being killed by Israelis (Jews) and are being forced to flee this nation. Nowadays, Palestinians are immigrants who are fleeing various nations, but regrettably, they are also in difficulties and in appalling conditions. They just lack agency and are even denied their most fundamental rights. In light of this circumstance, a quick overview of the past and current of Palestinian Muslim persecution is provided in this article.

Keywords: Palestine, Refugees, Israel, Jewish State, Hamas.

Introduction of Palestine:

Palestine is a territory in the eastern Mediterranean that includes the Palestinian territories of the West Bank and Gaza Strip, which are located along the Mediterranean coast, as well as portions of modern-day Israel (west of the Jordan River). This little territory, which some have claimed also includes Jordan, has been variously and sometimes controversially connected with the word Palestine. Over the span of over three millennia, both the political position and the geographic territory denoted by the term have changed. The area is revered by Muslims, Christians, and Jews and is also known as the Holy Land, at least in part. It has been the target of competing claims from Jewish and Arab national groups since the 20th century; this dispute has resulted in protracted bloodshed and, on many occasions, actual warfare.¹

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Population

The United Nations General Assembly passed the partition resolution of Palestine on November 29, 1947 and divided it into two states. Among these areas, the West Bank of the Jordan River and the Gaza Strip are under the control of the Palestinian Authority and the rest of the area is under the control of Israel. According to this separation, the population of Israel, which was around 14 lakhs in 1950, increased to 60 lakhs in 2000 because Jews have moved from all over the world and settled in Israel. About 24 million lived in the West Bank of the Jordan River and 15 million in the Gaza Strip.² The State of Palestine's midyear population as of May 26, 2021, was 5,227,193, according to the Palestinian Central Bureau of Statistics (PCBS).³ According to PCBS President Ala Owad, there will be 5.3 million people living there by the end of 2021.⁴

Importance of Palestine

Palestine is important for the three major religions of the world, Judaism, Christianity and Islam. For the Jews, this region is very sacred and important.⁵ However, during the time of Jesus, because the Jews were slaves of the Romans, they were always involved in conspiracies against the Romans. The Roman generals used to suppress them severely from time to time due to which they migrated.⁶ A number of them fled from here to Europe, Asia, and Africa, but they always had this deal in their minds that they would return to Jerusalem and establish their own government because they considered it their birthright. Palestine is also very sacred for Christians because in this region is "Bethlehem" where Jesus was born⁷ and it is also dear to the hearts of Islam and Muslims because it is from Jerusalem that the Holy Prophet ascended to the Ascension and it was the abode of other prophets.⁸ It is also an honour. In addition to this, traveling to only three places in Islam is a source of reward and reward: Haram al-Sharifeen and 3rd Haram , i.e. Bayt al-Maqdis.⁹

Palestinian Muslims

During the time of Hazrat Umar, the Muslims besieged Bait al-Maqdis, but the Christians, on the condition that the Caliph himself comes and makes a treaty with us, we will hand over the city to the Muslims. In 635 AD, Hazrat Umar visited Bait-ul-Maqdis with only one slave and one camel. He said in front of the entire congregation,¹⁰ "O inhabitants of the holy city, the rights and privileges that are for us are also for you, and the duties and responsibilities that are imposed on us are also obligatory on you." ¹¹

After the Caliphs of the Rashiduns, the land remained under the control of Palestine bin Umayyah. The Umayyad Caliph Abd al-Mulk bin Marwan built a beautiful mosque on the rock from where the Prophet started his ascension journey, called "Dom of the Rock".¹² The Abbasid caliphs also took part in the construction and development and beauty of Bait al-Maqdis in their time. In 969, this area came under the control of the Fatimid caliphs of Egypt

But in 1095, during the reign of Caliph Mustansar Ballah, after many years of religious battles with the Christians, the Christians recaptured Jerusalem with the help of the whole of Europe and shed so much blood of the Muslims that the horses of the Christians were soaked in the blood of the Muslims up to their ankles.¹³ A historian writes;

“in the Temple and porch of Solomon men rode in blood up to their knees and bridle reins.....In this temple 10,000 were killed. Indeed, if you had been there you would have seen our feet coloured to our ankles with the blood of the slain. But what more shall I relate? None of them were left alive; neither women nor children were spared.”¹⁴

After many years of crusades, at the end of 1192, Salah al-Din Ayubi, the ruler of Egypt, took back Beit Al-Maqdis from the Christians.¹⁵

The Mamluks were the rulers of Palestine from 1270 to 1516.¹⁶ In 1517, the Turks conquered the region and remained under their rule until 1917.¹⁷ The Turkish Caliph Sultan Abd al-Hamid was lured by the Jews and especially by the Jewish nobleman Dr. Theodor Herzl, who offered huge sums of money, rewards and some debts.¹⁸ The United States likewise made every effort to permit Jews to live in Palestine; however, Sultan Abdul Hamid retorted firmly that Jews would never be permitted to dwell in the Kingdom of Palestine as long as the Ottoman Empire remains in place. In order to make it easier to remove the Jews from Palestine after three months, he issued red passports only for them. He also started to become more rigorous and ordered the Jews to leave the country after three months. And the next year, he issued another proclamation prohibiting Jews from purchasing even a single square inch of land in Palestine. As a result, the Jews of America and Western imperialism planned to kill Sultan Abdul Hamid II and abolish its government. They tried to destroy the Sultan's car with a car full of gunpowder, but Allah saved the Sultan. But due to the conspiracy of Jews, they succeeded in dethroning the Sultan in 1909 by the enlightened Turks.¹⁹ Following that, the French and then the British were able to seize Palestine. The Jews had vowed to give the British the territory of Palestine and had supported them throughout World War I, thus in 1917 Prime Minister of British Empire, Arthur James Balfour had promised Jewish to make sure establishment of a Jewish state in Palestine by an official letter which is called “Balfour Declaration”.²⁰

Jews were granted unrestricted freedom by British High Commissioner Samuel to purchase land in Palestine, settle there, and take use of the country's mineral reserves.²¹ When Churchill visited Palestine in March 1931, the Palestinians presented their demands. The sale and purchase of land in Palestine should be banned. Palestine should not be separated from its original countries, but Churchill insisted on accepting the "Balfour Declaration" in any case.²²

After 1919, not only did the Jews start migrating to Palestine very quickly,²³ but the rich lands were also bought in droves and Jewish settlements were also settled in haste. The Palestinians were driven to sell their land by the harsh economic policies and taxes

implemented by the British administration. By the end of 1945, the United States had joined this conflict as well, surpassing Britain in the process. Because America was now the leader of all of Europe following the Second World War and was entirely influenced by the Jewish people. With all of their power, the Jews were putting forth demands to the United States and Great Britain.²⁴

Partition of Palestine

Under the influence of these countries, Palestine was finally divided in 1948. Ahmad Taha writes in his book "The Tragedy of Jerusalem":

*"On November 29, 1947, the United Nations adopted the resolution which recommended the partition of Palestine into a Jewish State, an Arab State, and an International Zone of Jerusalem under United Nations' Control, each one with fixed boundaries by 15th of May 1948."*²⁵

According to their scheduled program, on May 15, 1948, the British government announced the withdrawal from Palestine and announced the withdrawal of its troops.²⁶ Immediately after that, the Jews announced the establishment of the State of Israel. First America and then Russia recognized Israel, after those other European countries also recognized the existence of Israel. However, there was no longer any justification for the Englishman to stay here because he had completed that mission. Now the power here and most of the factories, businesses, banks, shops and economy were under the control of the Jews and this is what the British wanted. In view of providing security to Israel, on May, 1950, the three major Western countries of the world, the United States, England, and France, issued a joint statement in which they supported Israel and guaranteed the protection of their rights at all costs. And in this statement, it was said that Israel will help Western countries to establish peace and order in the Middle East. These countries declared that action would be taken against any government in the region that attempted to use or threaten force against Israel, and that any country that violated the Rhodes Peace Agreement or No change will be allowed. In this statement, it was also said that the Arab countries and Israel will not have the authority to compete in the field of arms, only in view of defence purposes, weapons will be allowed to go to these countries. Governments have guaranteed Israel's existence and legally recognized the usurpation of other people's land.²⁷

The chronicle of atrocities on Palestinians

By the way, the whole Palestinian narrative is better than the gloom of tyranny, torture, and incarceration. The Palestinian people have endured tyranny for a century and more since 1971. Only the most well-known incidents of this persecution tale—which starts with "Revolutionary Buraq"—will be briefly discussed here. On August 14, 1929, Jews held a large demonstration in Tal Aviv to commemorate the destruction of the Temple of Solomon, followed by another large demonstration in Jerusalem the next day. And their

demonstrations ignited the fire of the "Baraq Revolution". On the second day, Palestinian Muslims gathered in large numbers in the compound of the Al-Aqsa Mosque (coincidentally, it was Friday and the day of Milad al-Nabi, and then this grand gathering was a procession. departed from the Al-Aqsa Mosque in the form of and demolished what the Jews had built around the Baraq Wall.²⁸

Small skirmishes continued until the second Friday, August 23, 1929, saw a major explosion known as the "Baraq Revolution". The Arabs attacked a large number of Jews, as a result of which the British army attacked the Arabs with various types of weapons and warplanes. This series of riots and clashes spread from the city of Quds to other cities and villages. Arrived, Palestine saw for the first time such a week of bloodshed among the Arabs.²⁹

Since the establishment of the Israeli state in 1948, Israel has always continued the mission of genocide of the Palestinians and killed them with various pretexts. He always called for peace in Israel. Now see how the advocate of peace and order established peace and order.

- On January 6, 1952, Jews were massacred in Beit Jala.³⁰
- In December 1952, the Jews bombed an Arab town "Iqrat" near the Lebanese border and did not allow the patriotic residents to take shelter in the nearby villages and forced them to migrate to Lebanon.
- The Qibya massacre took place in October 1953 as part of Operation Shoshana, a retaliation operation in which Palestinian citizens were slain by Israeli forces commanded by Ariel Sharon when they stormed the hamlet of Qibya in the West Bank, which was then governed by Jordan. Over sixty-nine Palestinian civilians were slaughtered by Israeli soldiers, comprising women and children for two thirds.³¹
- In September 1953, the Jews razed the Rayhaniah settlement and pushed its inhabitants to the Syrian border.
- In March 1954, the incident of massacre of Nahalin took place.
- In February 1955, Jewish soldiers stormed into a refugee camp in the Gaza Strip in the dead of night, opening fire on unsuspecting Arabs sleeping contentedly in the tent.
- On April 5, 1956, the Jews turned their heavy artillery towards Gaza and destroyed it.
- On September 25, 1956, they attacked a town called "Hossan" on the border of Jordan and brutally killed the residents.³²

The horrors of Sabra and Shatila camps:

On September 15, 1982, Israeli tanks surrounded the two large Palestinian camps of Sabra and Shatila in Lebanon, and then in these camps, killing and killing and playing such a terrible game of death that humanity shuddered. During the first few hours of September 16, 1982, Jewish forces killed hundreds of Palestinians, shooting at anything that moved, killing entire families, children, the elderly, there was no difference between men and women, these people did not stop at killing, but in most cases, they dismembered their

limbs before killing them, these soldiers put the heads of children and boys on the walls. De Mara These soldiers committed adultery with women and daughters and then slaughtered them with axes. As for the Israeli forces, they blocked all the entrances to the tent so that no one could escape. Statistics show that more than 3,000 people died in this tragedy, while according to Palestinian estimates, this number is 30,000.³³

The Contemporary Situation of the Palestinian Underprivileged: An Overview

This game of cruelty and brutality is still going on in Palestine today. Palestinian Muslims are being killed by the Jewish lobby day by day or are forced to migrate continuously. Newspapers and social websites keep reporting the atrocities on Palestinian Muslims. Here are their highlights.

Brutal killing of disabled Palestinian leader Ahmed Yassin: Israel had attacked Ahmed Yassin more than once and was constantly threatening him that he was on our hit list. But despite his handicap, he never backed down from his mission and fear never approached him. He used to go daily in a wheelchair to the nearby mosque to pray without fear. On January 14, 2004, a Mujahid named "Raim Rishi" detonated a suicide bomb that killed four Israelis. Israel held Ahmed Yassin responsible for this incident. Ahmed Yassin refused, but the Israeli Deputy Defence Minister announced that Ahmed Yassin was on his hit list. He used to accuse that Yasin's hand is behind all the suicide attacks on Israelis and often Israeli civilians are killed. Ahmed Yasin's answer was that Israelis don't kill Palestinian civilians. This is the reward of exchange. On March 22, 2004, he was leaving the mosque on a wheelchair after offering morning prayers when an Israeli helicopter fired a missile at him. He was martyred on the spot. Along with him, his two body guards and 9 other worshipers were also martyred who were leaving the mosque after offering prayers. Another 12 men were injured, including two of Yasin's sons.³⁴

Israel's brutal bombing and blockade of Gaza: Israel keeps bombing Gaza mercilessly every day. 2014 Ramadan saw Israeli aeroplanes strike Gaza. In order to protect themselves from potential airstrikes, people lie down. A few were sprinting to seek refuge behind the protection of structures. Explosions sounded loud. The air rattled and the ground rocked. Screams could be heard everywhere as whirlwinds of fire and dust that could be seen from a distance emerged in the sky. Many who arrived at their destination covered in blood got to paradise. There were men, women, and children among the martyrs. These were hardly unfamiliar skies in this area. These tanks, armoured vehicles, artillery, and aeroplanes are routinely used to murder innocent civilians.³⁵

Later, Prime Minister of Israel, Benjamin Netanyahu, with the help of the US-supplied ground forces equipped with warplanes, guided missiles, cluster bombs and other sophisticated weapons, brutally and barbarically attacked the Muslims in different areas of Gaza without any hindrance. The massacre continued. Every day, a large number of funerals took place and the heart-felt cries and sighs of mothers, sisters and wives echoed in the

town of Gaza. On one side there were merciless tyrants armed with modern weapons and on the other hand the Muslims. How could they fight the fanatic killers? The war-crazed Israeli rulers killed more than two and a half thousand Muslims in these attacks. A large number of them (800/700) are children. The number of injured was 15/14 thousand without exaggeration. The Israeli government has deliberately targeted kindergartens, schools, hospitals, orphanages, mosques, and refugee camps. They attacked water supply lines, power plants and institutions providing basic needs, plunging the entire township into darkness. Israeli warplanes also used gas bombs during this time and killed civilian lives. Due to their brutal actions, food, water and medicine became scarce. Due to the siege of Gaza, these oppressed and innocent people could not get any kind of help from anywhere. The fanatical Israeli prime minister, Netanyahu, used the excuse for the massacre and genocide of oppressed Palestinian Muslims that the bodies of three missing youths had been found, and that these Jewish youths had been killed by Hamas. After that, some extremist Jews tortured and martyred a Palestinian youth. Although Hamas denied the accusation that they had killed Jewish youths, Israel did not make excuses for the killing of these youths, but Israel shed thousands of Muslims' blood in Gaza, Israeli Prime Minister Netanyahu said. That he will not stop the attacks on Gaza.³⁶

Who is not familiar with the aggression of Israel on Palestine in the beginning of July 2014? In this war that lasted for about 50 days, the Palestinians had to lose their homes, children, lives and property. According to the United Nations Relief and Works Agency, more than 1500 buildings were destroyed by this cruel action of Israel, whose reconstruction was started, but a few days ago, the United Nations also ended the process of providing roofs to the Palestinians saying that the funds for construction and repair are insufficient. Still, many people live without a shelter. How many children are living and have died of frostbite. Why don't they show the children of Palestine to those who build air bases and run UNICEF in more than a hundred countries of the world? According to the report of an Israeli human rights organization, more than 70 percent of those killed in the Israeli aggression in 2014 were children, women and the elderly. According to the organization, 2014 was the most difficult year for Palestinian children. According to the same organization, more than 89,000 houses were destroyed, 15,000 of which were not repaired.³⁷

While Israel has targeted children, women, and the elderly in self-imposed war situations, it has been targeting children in normal situations as well. 14-year-old Palestinian girl *Malak al-Khatib* had been arrested for the "crime" of throwing stones at armed IDF.³⁸

In August 2014, 650 Palestinians were martyred and more than 4,000 were injured, while hundreds of homes, schools, residential buildings and mosques were turned into piles of rubble. Israeli Defence Minister Gabi Ashgai announced that Gaza will die brick by brick. Unlike the 2008 and 2012 attacks, a ground attack was also carried out this time. The Israeli forces attacked Gaza from different sides, including tanks and heavy weapons. Some analysts have written that a few years ago, vast reserves of oil and gas were discovered in

the Gaza Strip. Israel wants to take them under its control, so it wants to take control of Gaza at any cost.³⁹

The British newspaper The Guardian, in its publication of July 9, 2014, quoted the well-known defence analyst Dr. Naseer Ahmed as saying that Israel's energy crisis may intensify by 2020, in view of which Israel considers it necessary to occupy the Palestinian reserves. This is the reason why he has imposed war on Gaza to eliminate Hamas.⁴⁰

The horrors of Israeli prisons for women and children: Since 1948, millions of Palestinians have been put behind bars periodically, including thousands of women and children, who are subjected to all kinds of brutality and torture. Tactics such as sexual assault, naked interrogation, blackmail through lure and intimidation, and brutal torture during interrogation are used against Palestinian women held in Israeli prisons. In Israeli prisons, the biggest problem for Muslim women is the lack of gender discrimination. He also tried to commit suicide, but it has no effect on the Zionist beasts. Women are subjected to severe violence like men, due to which many women have also become martyrs. Ironically, the Israeli administration does not hand over the bodies of these martyred women to their heirs. Among the thousands of people imprisoned in Israeli prisons, where older people are included, children under the age of 18 have also been illegally detained. Currently, hundreds of Palestinian children are deprived of basic human rights in Israeli prisons. The Zionist police also arrests more than seven hundred Palestinian children every year. According to the report released by the Center for the Study of Prisoners, the Zionist forces detained a total of 100 women in the year 2015. Among them are young girls.⁴¹

According to the report published by International Women's Rights, 15,000 Palestinian women are currently being brutalized by Jewish soldiers in Israeli prisons.⁴²

Palestinian women in Israeli prisons suffer from dangerous diseases: "Maqab", an active organization for women's rights in Palestine, has expressed deep concern over the Zionist atrocities on Palestinian women imprisoned in Israeli prisons, revealing that the women imprisoned in the notorious "Hasharon" prison are suffering from many deadly diseases. while the Zionist administration is using their illnesses as a tactic of torture.⁴³

The plight and problems of Palestinian refugees: In the Arab-Israeli war of 1948, many cities were completely evacuated from Gaza, so the Palestinians migrated to different areas, but unfortunately, they were not allowed to live comfortably even in the refugee camps. Even today, millions of Palestinians are refugees in different countries. The refugees are lying in the camps and they are facing the worst situation there. During the ongoing civil war in Syria since 2011, along with the local population, a large number of Palestinian refugees living in the camps established by the United Nations as refugees in Syria. It has also become the fuel of war. Palestine. Recent figures have been released by the Syria Action Group, which shows that 3,275 Palestinian refugees living in Syria have died during the past five years. Released by the London-based Syria and Palestine Action Group. It is stated in the

report that Palestinians who were martyred in Syria were attacked in every way. They were targeted in the bombing. They were tortured and killed in prisons. Direct shots were fired and hundreds of Palestinians were martyred and injured during the fighting between the warring parties. The report states that the siege of Syrian cities by the government army is a major reason for the martyrdom of Palestinians. A large number of Palestinian children and sick civilians died due to lack of food and medicine.⁴⁴

According to United Nations statistics, 2.1 million of the 5 million Palestinian refugees are in Jordan, 1.3 million in Gaza, 9.14 thousand in the West Bank of the Jordan River, 5.00 million in Syria and 4.47 million in Lebanon.⁴⁵ The Commissioner General of the United Nations Organization for Palestine Refugees (UNRWA) Philip Grandi said during the news conference that at the moment, 400,000 to 550,000 Palestinian refugees in the border area of Syria are suffering from serious problems, who need cash, food, medicines and other things. The necessities of life are in dire need. He said that international aid of 91 million dollars has been received so far for the Palestinian refugees trapped in Syria, which is insufficient. In such situations, the lives of the Palestinian refugees have become miserable, so Jordan should Open your borders to the Palestinians.⁴⁶

According to the report of the Relief and Works Agency for Palestinians "UNRA", typhoid fever became epidemic in the besieged Yarmouk camp in Damascus and six cases had been confirmed there in the past period. There were also reliable reports of typhoid outbreaks in Yarmouk, Yalda and the two suburbs of Babula and Beit Saham. According to the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, typhoid could be life-threatening.⁴⁷

The plights of Palestinians in 2017

According to a report on May 22, 2017, a group of Jewish settlers in Israel attacked Buren villages in the city of Nablus on the Jordan River, as a result of which a Palestinian was injured and a car was also damaged. There are occasional clashes between Jewish settlers and residents of Buren. Even before that, Jewish settlers attacked Palestinian villages, set fire to several vehicles, and on Thursday killed a Palestinian while shooting at a rally to express solidarity with Palestinian prisoners. According to the Palestinian Red Crescent, 13 Palestinians were martyred and 13 injured in an attack by Israeli soldiers on the worshippers who were performing the Isha prayer at the entrance of the Al-Aqsa Mosque on the night of July 26, 2017. According to reports, after offering the Isha prayer at Bab-e-Isbat, the Israeli police mobilized and dispersed the congregation using stun grenades, rubber bullets and tear gas. According to eyewitnesses, the police stopped the journalists from covering the incident and detained a photojournalist after the beating. It should be clear that the Israeli police arrested 3 Palestinians with the claim of an armed attack in the Al-Aqsa Mosque on Friday, July 14. After the incident, the Israeli forces closed the mosque for worship.⁴⁸

According to the New York Times report of December 6, 2017, the end of the recent cruelty and excesses regarding Palestine is that the President of the United States, Donald Trump, announced on Wednesday night that he would recognize Jerusalem as the capital of Israel, and explained that this move was the United States' decision. It was necessary for the best interest of Israel and the establishment of peace between Israel and Palestine. According to him, this decision should have been made long ago. Supporting this decision of the United States, the Israeli Prime Minister said that our people in every corner of the world want to return to Jerusalem. And today Trump's announcement made it a historic day for us. Jerusalem is the center of our hopes, dreams and prayers.

On the other hand, this decision of the American President was severely criticized at the international level. Palestine Liberation Organization, Turkey, Egypt and France rejected this decision, calling it a violation of international laws and UN resolutions. Against the American announcement, thousands of Palestinians protested on the strike streets in the Hebron and Al-Bira regions of West Jordan. The demonstrators chanted "Jerusalem is the capital of the Palestinian state."⁴⁹ 31 Palestinians were injured.

The plights of Palestinians in 2023

In November 2023, once again Palestine-Israel war started and since the fighting began on October 7, over 12,000 people have died, 42 of whom were journalists, as of November 15. These casualties were occurred in only Gaza Strip while Israel's troops and settlers murdered 178 Palestinians in the West Bank.⁵⁰ There have been references to the humanitarian situation in Gaza as a "crisis" and a "catastrophe." Due to Israel's embargo and Hamas's resource hoarding, Gaza is experiencing a lack of supplies for food, medicine, fuel, water, and medical equipment.⁵¹ Israel did not spare the children, women injured on Gaza strip and targeted continually to hospitals. As a newspaper report;

“The largest hospital in Gaza, where up to 50,000 people are sheltering, is facing bombardment, the World Health Organization has said, as the US’s top diplomat said “far too many Palestinians have been killed” in the war.”⁵²

According to current situation of Gaza strip, hundreds of people have been killed by bombardment from Israeli force on various hospitals of Gaza. Israeli troops not only destroyed medicine depot but demolished many patients’ rooms as well.

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